

OS Awards

European Public Recognition Scheme for Open Source SW/HW Initiatives

European Open Source Academy (EOSA) Constitution

Project Deliverable D4.1

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Deliverable Abstract

The European Open Source Academy Constitution establishes the foundational governance framework for Europe's premier institution recognising excellence in Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware, and Open Technology more broadly. Initially funded by the European Commission from 2024-2027, the Academy is designed to transition into an independent Belgian non-profit organisation by 2026.

This document provides the framework for the Academy's first two years as part of the OS Awards.eu project, with provisions for regular review and amendment to ensure continued relevance as the organisation matures into full independence as a legal entity. The Constitution will necessarily evolve to accommodate applicable legal provisions in Belgian law relating to the ASBL institutional structure.

1 Deliverable Information

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1.2. About OS Awards.EU

OS Awards.EU is a 30-month initiative dedicated to establishing an European Open Source Academy and a prominent European Public Recognition Scheme for Open Source Software (OS SW) and Hardware (HW). By creating the annual European Open Source Awards, guided by the expert European Open Source Academy, the project will celebrate outstanding contributions and foster greater interest, integration, utilisation, and exploitation of OS assets across Europe.

Strategically leveraging the EU Open Source Week alongside key European events, the project will amplify the awards’ profile and engage the community. The European OS Academy, in collaboration with the European Commission, will ensure award legitimacy and drive open source skills development. By intertwining recognition, legitimacy, and community engagement, OS Awards.EU aims to cultivate a comprehensive strategy that drives innovation, advances open source technologies, enhances EU competitiveness, and strengthens its open strategic autonomy.

OS Awards.eu Partners

The **OS Awards.eu** consortium consists of 7 partners from six different European countries:

1. RISE RESEARCH INSTITUTES OF SWEDEN AB (RISE), Sweden
2. OPENFORUM EUROPE (OFE), Belgium
3. FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION (TECNALIA), Spain
4. TRUST-IT SERVICES SRL (Trust-IT), Italy
5. BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION (BSC CNS), Spain
6. ASSOCIATION PROFESSIONNELLE EUROPEENNE DU LOGICIEL LIBRE (APELL asbl), Belgium
7. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN

2 Executive Summary

The **European Open Source Academy Constitution** establishes the foundational governance framework for Europe's premier institution recognising excellence in Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware, and Open Technology more broadly. Initially funded by the European Commission from 2024-2027, the Academy is designed to transition into an independent Belgian non-profit organisation by 2026.

This document provides the **framework for the Academy's first two years** as part of the OSAwards.eu project, with provisions for regular review and amendment to ensure continued relevance as the organisation matures into full independence as a legal entity. The Constitution will necessarily evolve to accommodate applicable legal provisions in Belgian law relating to the ASBL institutional structure.

Core Mission: The Academy provides public recognition for individuals and organizations advancing Europe's open source communities through four strategic pillars: Excellence and Achievement, Business and Impact, Advocacy and Awareness, and Skills and Education. The core goal of the Academy is to provide Public Recognition of those individuals and organisations elevating, representing, advocating for, and contributing to the advancement of the European Open Source Software and Hardware communities, as well as the ecosystem of Open Technologies more broadly.

Through its activities, the Academy strives to amplify, promote, and reward outstanding contributions to the Open Source Software and Hardware communities across Europe, elevating them for recognition by an esteemed audience of policymakers, industry, and society-at-large, thereafter serving as a hub for advocacy, awareness, education, and outreach related to the aforementioned topics.

Governance Structure:

- The **European Open Source Academy** is a member-driven organisation aiming to improve Public Recognition, with **Academy Members** serving for life with voting rights on major decisions.
- The **European Open Source Academy Constitution** will be updated upon its incorporation into a legal entity in 2026, and thereafter every five (5) years. This document provides an initial framework agreed with its members, serving as the organisational and cultural basis for its legal Constitution.
- The major activity of the Academy is the organisation of the **European Open Source Awards**, from which the honored members will be invited to join the Academy.
- The **Academy Council** consists of twelve (12) elected members serving three-year terms, organised into four sections: Excellence and Achievement, Business and Impact, Advocacy and Awareness, and Skills and Education.
- The **Academy Secretariat** provides operational support to the Academy and manages the annual European Open Source Awards. The size of the Secretariat is dependent on the fundraising and sustainability prospects of the Academy, but shall not include less than one (1) individual.
- The **Excellence and Achievement Section** is designated with special responsibilities and

includes a President , General-Secretary, and Treasurer who coordinate with the Academy Secretariat. The **Academy President** can serve (consecutively or non-consecutively) two terms.

- Further clarifications and elaboration of this Constitution will be enacted through subsequent **Rules of Procedure**, which will stipulate the conditions for enforcement of this provision.

Key Activities: The Academy organises the annual European Open Source Awards ceremony each January/February in Brussels during the EU Open Source Week, with awardees invited to join the membership. The sections of the Academy will be responsible for promoting its goal of Public Recognition through specific policy and advocacy goals which will be later enumerated.

Membership: Open to leading figures in open source communities with demonstrable EU connections. The initial twelve (12) members were appointed by an EC-designated consortium, with subsequent expansion through peer nomination processes beginning in 2025. Members will be invited upon receipt of a prize, award, or recognition at the European Open Source Awards, though members reserve the right to document conditions under which non-awardees can be invited to the European Open Source Academy.

3 European Open Source Academy Constitution

Chapter 0: Preamble

0.0. This Constitution sets forth the principles and rules governing the operation and structure of the European Open Source Academy for its first two years. During this time, the members of the Academy will work to position it as a self-sustaining, independent entity that can exist beyond the time the EU-funded OS Awards.eu project – which helps fund its initial setup – ends in 2027.

0.1. The European Open Source Academy (hereinafter ‘Academy’) has been established and funded at its outset by the European Commission in the period from 2024-2027, with the aim of becoming an independent and self-sustaining legal entity by 2027. The Academy will serve as Europe's premier institution for the advancement and recognition of European excellence in Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware, and Open Technology.

0.2. This Academy Constitution provides a comprehensive foundation for the establishment, objectives, governance, membership, and amendments of the Academy over its initial two-year period and will need to be revised in 2026, upon its incorporation as a legal entity.

0.3. The Academy Constitution aligns with those values, governance ideals, and principles set forth in the statutes of similar institutions, most notably those incorporated under the law governing European institutions in Belgium.

Chapter I: Establishment

Article I – Foundation

1.1. With this Constitution, the Academy is established under the auspices of the European Commission. The Academy brings together Members who have been recognised for celebrating and advancing excellence in Europe’s Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware, and Open Technology communities.

1.2. From its inception, the Academy will advance and enlarge its membership and community, most notably by bringing in, recognising, and amplifying the work of experts and luminaries from the Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware, and Open Technology communities across Europe. In doing so, the Academy will provide thought leadership for policymakers, industry, and society-at-large, in order to improve public recognition for, and communicate the value and impact of, Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware, and Open Technology for an audience of European policymakers and industry representatives.

Article II – Scope

2.1. The initial focus of the Academy will be on Open Source Software and Open Source Hardware, but its membership will welcome and be inclusive of individuals whose contributions inform other forms of Open Technologies, most notably (but not exclusively) Open Data, Open Standards, Open Source AI, and Open Content. The Academy will aim to represent not just Open Source Software and Open Source Hardware but also other Open Technologies over time in the membership and in the awarding of the Prize for Excellence in Open Source and other Special Recognitions and/or Honorary Awards at the annual European Open Source Awards.

2.2. The interpretation of this scope will be subject to the interpretation of Academy Members and subsequent Rules of Procedure, and there is scope to be formally updated during the revision of the Academy Constitution.

Article III – Legal Basis

3.1. While initially funded by the European Commission, the Academy will evolve into an independent not-for-profit organisation based in Belgium in 2026, with a roughly one year overlap with the OS Awards.eu project. A Belgian organisation has been chosen in order to ensure appropriate coordination with the European Commission and other appropriate European institutions. Specifically, the Academy will be incorporated as a Belgian ASBL in 2026, with the possibility of becoming an international AISBL in the years thereafter.

3.2. Future funding and sustainability of the Academy will be a high priority as it seeks to transition into an independent legal entity, and all decisions in the transition period 2025-2027 will be made in consultation with the European Commission.

Article IV – Funding

4.1. The Academy receives initial subsidy from the European Commission through a consortium project running from 2025-2027, with voluntary and non-remunerated contributions from Academy Members. The business model for the Academy will necessarily evolve over time to reflect the needs of the Academy and its members.

4.2. A plan for the future sustainability of the Academy will be drafted by the consortium Members appointed by the European Commission in coordination with the founding Academy Council Members, and will be used to guide the operations and financial sustainability of the Academy as an independent legal entity beginning in 2027.

Article V – Use of Funds

5.1. The Academy will never at any time make a profit, and all funds will be used to support the activities of the Academy, including (but not necessarily limited to) the organisation of the European Open Source Awards, research projects, outreach programmes, and travel.

5.2. While Academy Members are non-remunerated, Members of the Academy Council may receive stipends depending on the financial prospects of the Academy. The decision to provide a stipend, and the amount, is at the discretion of a vote of the Academy Members and will be made in consultation with the Academy Secretariat at the beginning of each year.

Chapter II: Objectives

Article VI – Goals

6.1. The core goal of the Academy is to provide Public Recognition of those individuals and organisations elevating, representing, advocating for, and contributing to the advancement of the European Open Source Software and Hardware communities, as well as the ecosystem of Open Technologies more broadly. Through its activities, the Academy strives to amplify, promote, and reward outstanding contributions to the Open Source Software and Hardware communities across Europe, elevating them for recognition by an esteemed audience of policymakers, industry, and society-at-large, thereafter serving as a hub for advocacy, awareness, education, and outreach related to the aforementioned topics.

6.2. Academy Members will advance and uphold the principle of Public Recognition, whereby new Members, awards, and projects are selected by the other Academy Members based on merit, ensuring the legitimacy and integrity of the Awards, and that these same values unify and guide the Academy’s work on Excellence and Achievement, Business and Impact, Advocacy and Awareness, and Skills and Education activities (see Articles VII, VIII, and IX).

6.3. Within the broader framework of Public Recognition, the Academy will strive to advance four sub-goals:

- a) **Excellence and Achievement:** Promoting the celebration of excellence and achievement within the European Open Source Software/Open Source Hardware communities.
- b) **Business and Impact:** Advancing the conditions for entrepreneurship and a sustainable business ecosystem around Open Source Software and Hardware, and its impact to the society and economy of Europe in particular and the world at large,
- c) **Advocacy and Awareness:** Advocating for the interests of Open Source Software and Hardware communities, as well as positively advancing the representation of European contributions to these communities and representing their interests in global fora.
- d) **Skills and Education:** Growing and upskilling representatives of the Open Source Software and Hardware communities, onboarding and empowering new generations of contributors to both communities, and creating opportunities for connecting with educational and outreach programmes.

These four sub-goals correspond to the four Sections of the Academy’s Council, outlined below. Subsequent activities within the scope of the Excellence and Achievement, Business and Impact, Advocacy and Awareness, and Skills and Education Sections will be defined separately and ratified by Academy Members through its Rules of Procedure.

6.4. Aligning with the principle of Public Recognition, the Academy will run the annual European Open Source Awards. The annual European Open Source Awards ceremony will take place in late January or early February each year in Brussels, Belgium, in alignment with the EU Open Source Week. All awardees of the Academy will be invited to join the Academy, and can either accept the invitation or decline to join. The European Open Source Awards ceremony will be organised primarily by a consortium appointed by the European Commission in the period 2025-2027, with support from the Academy Members. The Academy Secretariat will become solely responsible for the running of the European Open Source Awards ceremony beginning in 2028.

Chapter III: Governance

Article VII – Academy Membership

7.1. Academy Members, once appointed to the Academy, serve for life. Members may resign at any time (as outlined in Article XVI).

7.2. The Academy is at its core a member-driven organisation and aims to be beneficial to its members. Academy Members (who are not part of the Academy Council) have no obligations or requirements for participation, aside from participation in annual General Assemblies and having voting rights on important decisions. Any more specific benefits of membership will be enacted through subsequent

Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate the conditions for enforcement of this provision.

7.3. Academy Members will have voting rights and vote in General Elections (beginning at the first GA in 2026), voting on matters such as (but not exclusively): the election of new Academy President, General-Secretary, and Treasurer; the nomination and appointment of Academy Council Members; changes related to the Rules of Procedure; and the interpretation and adjudication of disputes related to the interpretation of the implementation or interpretation of the Academy Constitution and Rules of Procedure.

7.4. The first twelve (12) Academy Members were appointed by a consortium of European actors, supporting the establishment of the Academy on behalf of the European Commission.

7.5. The Peer Nomination Process will be defined separately and included in its Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate the conditions for the enforcement of this provision. The process will outline the process for the initial enlargement of the Academy in 2025, as well as the initial conditions by which awardees of the European Open Source Awards will be invited to join the Academy. It will also document conditions under which non-awardees can be invited to the European Open Source Academy.

Article VIII – Academy Council

8.1. The Academy Council will govern the Academy and consist of elected Council Members, who serve three (3) year terms as part of the Council.

8.2. Only twelve (12) Academy Members will serve in the Academy Council at any given time.

8.3. The Academy Council will consist of four sections: Excellence and Achievement, Business and Impact, Advocacy and Awareness, and Skills and Education. The Excellence and Achievement section will comprise one (1) Academy President, one General-Secretary, and one Treasurer,, who play a leading role in coordinating with the Academy Secretariat on behalf of the Academy Council. The Academy Council will also include three (3) Section Heads, and six (6) Section Officers for a total of thirteen (12) Members of the Academy Council. The Council constitutes the *de jure* Leadership of the Academy Council and will be extended additional responsibilities, to be defined by the Section Heads in cooperation with their sections, and defined through the Rules of Procedure.

8.4. The role of the Academy President, General-Secretary, and Treasurer will be to lead the drafting of the Rules of Procedure and to lead in the delegation of tasks and oversight of all operational matters and responsibilities of the Academy, in coordination with the Academy Secretariat. Additionally, the General-Secretary will be responsible for organising Academy meetings and handling administrative and policy matters. The Treasurer will be responsible for all matters related to internal finance management and accountability.

8.5. All roles and responsibilities in Sections besides the Excellence and Achievement Section (see Article XII below) are discretionary and will be defined in a process and timeline to be defined by the Academy Council Members and enacted through subsequent Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

8.6. An Organisational Chart with roles for Academy Council Members, as well as terms for the enforcement of the provisions of the Articles in this Constitution, will be enacted through subsequent

Rules of Procedure, which will outline this process and stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision. The Rules of Procedure must be updated and re-authorised at least one (1) time per annum at the first annual GA meeting in January.

Article IX – Academy Secretariat

9.1. The Academy will be supported at all times by a core staff, consisting of at least one (1) individual, responsible for the general management and administration of Academy operations. The number of Academy Secretariat staff will be decided and approved by the Academy Council Members, in accordance with the financial conduct of the institution.

9.2. The role of the Academy Secretariat will be to lead fundraising and administration of the Academy, organise Academy meetings, facilitate events and promotion of Academy activities, and lead the planning of the annual European Open Source Awards ceremony. Additional responsibilities will be outlined in the Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate the conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

9.3. The Academy Council will until 1 February 2027 be assisted by a Consortium of neutral European actors, supporting the establishment of the Academy on behalf of the European Commission, which will act as proxy to the Academy Secretariat.

Article X – Meetings and Quorum

10.1. The Academy will hold biannual General Assembly meetings (online or in-person) to discuss matters related to the enlargement and operations of the Academy (each Spring) and the nomination and organisation of the European Open Source Awards (each Fall). The content of these meetings and the nature of the matters requiring votes will be enacted through subsequent Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

10.2. Voting decisions will be overseen by the Academy President, with the General-Secretary serving as Rapporteur, and voting decisions will require a quorum of at least half of the convened Academy Members in order to vote. Academy Members are not obliged to attend but may miss out on input to the conduct of Academy activities.

10.3. The Academy will hold quarterly Academy Council meetings, at least four times per year, with extraordinary meetings convened as needed. The Academy President or General-Secretary must be in attendance in order for the meeting to commence. Voting decisions will be overseen by the Academy President, with the General-Secretary serving as Rapporteur (or in their absence, a Member nominated by the President), and voting decisions will require a quorum of at least three-quarters (9) of the convened Council Members in order to vote. Non-availability of Academy Council Members should be communicated in writing in advance of each meeting. The content and frequency of these meetings will be enacted through subsequent Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

10.4. The Academy Secretariat will convene meetings with the Excellence and Achievement Section as needed for the conduct of operational activities. The specific purpose and cadence of these meetings will be enacted through subsequent Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

Article XI – Voting and Decision-Making

11.1. All decisions of the Academy and Academy Council – including (but not limited to) financial and

operational matters, decisions related to Awards and awardees, and the enforcement of remediation measures – will be made by majority vote.

11.2. In the event of a tie, the President will make the final decision, being allowed one additional vote to break the tie.

Article XII – Transparency and Accountability

12.1. Beginning in 2026, all decisions of the Academy will be documented in detailed meeting notes, prepared by the Academy Secretariat in consultation with the Academy General-Secretary or, when absent, the Academy President.

12.2. Detailed accounts of discussions held during Academy meetings will remain confidential and will not be released publicly unless otherwise agreed by the Academy Council Members.

12.3. Breaches of confidentiality will be addressed according to the Academy’s disciplinary procedures, which will be defined in a process and timeline to be defined by the Academy Council Members and enacted through subsequent Rules of Procedure, and which will stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

Article XIII – Conflict of Interest

13.1. Should the Academy be required to take a decision or a view on any operation within its mandate for which any Academy Member has any direct or indirect patrimonial interest that is contrary to the interests of the Academy itself, that Academy Member will be required to inform the Academy Council of the potential conflict of interest before the Board takes a decision or a view. The Academy Member’s declaration, as well as the explanations provided about the nature of the possible conflict of interest, must be recorded in the minutes of the respective Academy Council meeting. It is not allowed that the Academy Council delegates any such decision.

13.2. If the majority of the Academy Council Members affirm that the petitioning Academy Member has a conflict of interest, their voting privileges for that decision or operation will be suspended.

Chapter IV: Membership

Article XIV – Membership Conditions

14.1. Academy Membership is open to individuals who have made significant contributions to the Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware, and Open Technology communities, representing various fields, including Development and Engineering, Business and Impact, Skills and Education, and Advocacy and Awareness.

14.2. All Academy Members must be leading and respected figures in the broader Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware, and Open Technology communities. EU citizenship or residency is a prerequisite for consideration, and Members must have been shown to make demonstrable impact in Europe through their contributions to the global Open Source Software and Hardware community. For the purposes of this provision, demonstrable connections to the EU may be considered on a case-by-case basis. The Academy President and Section Heads have some discretion in enacting this directive, with the intention to allow for a small degree of subjectivity over time, depending on circumstances.

14.3. Disqualifying criteria will be defined by the Academy Council Members and will be enacted through subsequent Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

Article XV – Rules of Appointment

15.1. The first four (4) Academy Members will become de facto Academy Council Members and will be appointed by a Consortium designated by the European Commission, and carried out in close consultation with the European Commission.

15.2. During the first year of the Academy, eight (8) additional Academy Members will be appointed through rules governed by the Peer Nomination Process. Subsequent Academy Members will be invited upon receipt of a prize, award, or recognition at the European Open Source Awards, though members reserve the right to document conditions under which non-awardees can be invited to the European Open Source Academy.

15.3. Beginning on 1 February 2027, Academy Council Members will be elected through a process overseen by the full Academy Council, and will until 2027 be done in consultation with the European Commission. Every three years, Academy Council Members will be elected from the existing Academy membership, with the President, General-Secretary, Treasurer, Sections Heads, and Section Officers running specifically for those positions as part of qualifying for the Council.

15.4. The timeline for the election of Academy Council Members and appointment of all Academy Members will be enacted through subsequent Rules of Procedure, which will outline this process and stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

Article XVI – Academy Rotation

16.1. All Academy Members serve for life, unless they resign from the Academy (see Article IV, Section IV).

16.2. The Academy will introduce a regular rotation system for Academy Council Members, with terms of, in general, three (3) years, renewable each time by vote, including the Academy President, who will serve a term of three (3) years as well, but may only serve two (2) terms (either consecutively or non-consecutively). The Academy President may continue to serve in the Academy Council after their two terms, but only in a different capacity.

16.3. The term for initial founding Academy Members will last until 1 February 2027.

16.4. Given the outstanding nature of the first Academy Membership process, The term for the founding Academy Members will last until 1 February 2027. Beginning on 1 February 2027, subsequent Academy Council Members will serve for terms of three (3) years.

16.5. Both Academy Council Members and Academy Members more broadly may resign at any time during their term. Should they do so before the end of their term, a replacement will be nominated by the Academy President and ratified by a 2/3 vote of the Academy Council.

Article XVII – Academy Rotation

17.1. Academy Members will de jure have the right to vote on all matters involving the Academy as a whole (as opposed to the Academy Council more narrowly, unless otherwise appointed).

17.2. Academy Members cannot take part in votes anymore if they have become inactive. In this case, being inactive is defined as missing two (2) General Assembly meetings in a row. Academy Members must request to reactivate through a written request to the Academy President.

17.3. A process and timeline to be defined by the Academy Council Members and enacted through subsequent Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

Article XVIII – Resignation

18.1. Resignation from the Academy will be done in writing to the Academy President and will be effective from one (1) month after the date of notification. In the event that resignation results in the vacation of an Academy Council seat, that seat will be filled through a Special Election, as put forth in a process and timeline to be defined by the Academy Council Members and enacted through subsequent Rules of Procedure, and which will stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

18.2. Academy Council Members are not obliged to finish their term, and may resign their post while maintaining general Academy Membership. Similarly, that seat will be filled through a Special Election, as put forth in a process and timeline to be defined by the Academy Council Members and enacted through subsequent Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

Article XIX – Diversity and Representation

19.1. The Academy will commit itself to representing a diverse range of perspectives and identities, with particular attention to gender, geography, and field-specific diversity. Diversity is a strategic aim of the Academy, which aims to elevate the importance of different fields of diversity through its activities and embody those values through its Membership.

19.2. The Academy will aim to represent a diverse range of perspectives and identities in the activities of its Members, particularly the Academy Council Members. As part of the yearly update of the Rules of Procedure, the Academy will do an evaluation of the diversity of its membership and leadership and recommend corresponding remediation measures.

19.3. Academy Council Members should be broadly representative across North, West, Central, Southern, and Eastern Europe and should be broadly representative across backgrounds such as: developers and contributors; community managers and/or non-technical contributors; business leaders and industry; academia/civil society; and EU and Member State policymakers.

19.4. Necessarily, there is some degree of subjectivity in enacting these provisions, and other provisions relating to the broad diversity of the Academy will be interpreted and codified through subsequent Rules of Procedure, which will stipulate conditions for the enforcement of this provision.

Article XX – Academy Protocol

20.1. All Academy Members are expected to adhere to best practices in decorum and professional conduct. Specific provisions for how to do so will, where appropriate, be stipulated as part of the Rules of Procedure, which will contain a Code of Conduct.

Chapter V: Amendments to the Constitution

Article XXI – Review of Constitution

21.1. This Constitution will be reviewed every five (5) years to ensure it remains fit for purpose, reflecting the evolving nature of Open Source Software and Hardware technologies and governance, as well as changes in Academy leadership.

21.2. An exception to the five (5) year rule pertains to the requirement to update the Constitution to be fit for purpose as part of a Belgian ASBL structure, which may necessitate changes to this text to meet legal requirements. The five (5) year rule will then apply from the date of that new constitution, unless otherwise required by the applicable legal process.

Article XXV – Proposal of Amendments

25.1. Any member of the Academy may propose amendments to this Constitution.

25.2. Proposed amendments must be submitted in writing and require a two-thirds majority for approval during Academy General Assembly meetings.